

A P O L L O

D7.7: Dissemination Report I

WP7 – Exploitation and Communication

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Table of Contents

Executive summary.....	6
1 Communication activities and tools	7
1.1 Visual identity	7
1.1.1 Logo	7
1.1.2 Colour pallet	8
1.1.3 Templates.....	8
1.2 Website.....	11
1.2.1 Website statistics	17
1.3 Newsletter.....	20
1.4 APOLLO on Social Media	22
1.4.1 Twitter.....	22
1.4.2 Facebook.....	22
1.4.1 LinkedIn.....	23
2 Dissemination activities.....	24
2.1 Conferences	24
2.2 Publications	28
2.3 Media.....	28
2.3.1 Serbia.....	28
2.3.2 Greece.....	29
3 Conclusions	29
4 References	30
5 Annexes.....	31
Annex I: APOLLO Dissemination Report	31
Annex II: APOLLO's 1 st Newsletter	32

Table of Figures

Figure 1: APOLLO logo.....	7
Figure 2: APOLLO Colour Pallet	8
Figure 2: Deliverable document template.....	9
Figure 3: Non-deliverable document template.....	9
Figure 4: Deliverable document review template.....	10
Figure 5: Event report template.....	10
Figure 6: Press release template	11
Figure 7: Presentation template	11
Figure 8: APOLLO's web home page.....	12
Figure 9: News and tweets section	12
Figure 10: APOLLO project section preview.....	13

Figure 11: Concept section preview 13
Figure 12: Services section preview 14
Figure 13: Tillage Scheduling service section preview 14
Figure 14: Irrigation Scheduling service section preview 15
Figure 15: Crop Growth Monitoring service section preview 15
Figure 16: Crop Yield Estimation service section preview 15
Figure 17: Pilot section preview 16
Figure 18: Get Involved section and web page footer 17
Figure 19: Visitor sessions for the APOLLO website (launch-M06). 19
Figure 20: New and returning visitors (launch-M06). 19
Figure 21: Visits based on country of origin launch-M06). 20
Figure 22: APOLLO's 1st Newsletter editorial 21
Figure 23: APOLLO's Twitter page 22
Figure 24: APOLLO's Facebook page..... 23
Figure 25: APOLLO LinkedIn Group 23

Table of Tables

Table 1: Statistical indicators (launch-M06)..... 18
Table 2: Conferences and workshops at which APOLLO was represented (M0-M06)..... 28

Executive summary

The main objective of this deliverable is to **provide a comprehensive overview** of the dissemination, communication and marketing tools and activities developed during M0 – M06 of the APOLLO project. The overall objective of the dissemination and communication activities is to promote the results and benefits of the project to a range of relevant target audiences, in order to foster a sustainable customer base for the future commercial service.

The dissemination and communication material and activities that have been produced or undertaken during this period include:

- the visual identity of the project, established at the beginning of the project, aiming to set the baseline for a brand identity for the commercial service;
- a public website launched at M05 and regularly updated, to serve as a single source of information concerning the project results and activities, and to disseminate news;
- the APOLLO page on Facebook, the LinkedIn group and the APOLLO Twitter account, which provide platforms for communicating news and material related to APOLLO to specific audiences (e.g. younger, technologically-aware farmers on Facebook), and for sharing the latest information on the APOLLO services;
- the first of the project's trimonthly newsletters, providing information, results and events related to the project;
- specific dissemination tools used and distributed at external conferences (i.e. audience-focused presentations);
- representation in conferences and media as well as the publication of scientific papers, enhancing APOLLO's visibility and enabling the development of a solid network amongst agricultural and Earth Observation (EO) academic and industrial stakeholders at both European and regional level.

The aim of the networking activities is the exchange of information and the fostering of closer scientific and technological cooperation between the project partners and other academic, industrial and governmental partners in the field of Agriculture and Earth Observation services/applications, focused primarily on Europe. Strong networks of stakeholders in both fields is a necessary and important step in the harmonisation of activities and efforts to maximise regional stakeholder's awareness of APOLLO's services.

This document provides short descriptions of the dissemination and communication activities reported from APOLLO partners, and carried out directly by the WP7 team. These include participation in conferences, networking events, media, publications etc. The positive impacts of these activities are already being felt, as exemplified by the requests from media representatives for more information about the project (see Section 2.3).

1 Communication activities and tools

1.1 Visual identity

As defined in D7.1: Dissemination, communication and marketing plan, an integrated and coherent visual identity underpins all communication products and tools and forms the basis for a commercial brand. The visual identity consists of the logo, colour pallet, and additional visual elements (e.g. the green header bar) which work together to form a coherent and easily-recognisable whole.

By creating a comprehensive and clean logo, and investing in high-quality design, the WP7 team aims to maximise and prolong the attention and interest of target audiences, and convey the impression of a professional and operational undertaking, as opposed to a research project or a concept under development. In order to become widely recognisable as a brand with as much recognition and awareness as possible throughout the three years of the project, the visual identity has been designed to enable continuity between the project phase and the subsequent commercial phase. In other words, even if the name “APOLLO” is changed to better reflect the content of the services, the similarity of the graphic identity will ensure that brand recognition is retained.

As required by Horizon 2020 rules on dissemination (European Commission, 2012), across all the outputs of the APOLLO project, and accompanying the logo, text concerning the source of the project’s funding and disclosing the Grant Agreement number is provided, along with the European flag.

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1.1.1 Logo

A comprehensive review of future competitors’ logos (e.g. Pixagri, eLeaf) and those of other projects was undertaken. Some 50 logos were evaluated as part of this process. A design brief was developed in close coordination with the project coordinator. An iterative design and refinement process led to the creation of three options, of which the final version was selected by vote at the project’s Kick-Off Meeting (KOM). The final version is presented in **Error! Reference source not found.** below.

Figure 1: APOLLO logo

The logo is comprised of two components, the icon and the text. The symbolism of the icon is based on two components, the pixelated roots and the leaves growing from them. The roots symbolise the data on which the services are based, and imply that the plants’ development is “fed” by information. The plant itself represents healthy crops. Based on the clean and crisp look of the selected logo, the decision was taken not to include any subtext as part of the logo itself.

The text “APOLLO” is not entangled with any other visual element of the logo. This means that if the name is changed in the future to better reflect the commercial aim of the undertaking, the same graphic identity can be adopted without compromising any brand recognition achieved throughout the project.

1.1.2 Colour pallet

The colours used in the visual identity were selected based on the association of shades of green with living and healthy plants. The grey shade used for the font contrasts comfortably with the icon, and subtly suggests a sleek and modern aesthetic. The APOLLO colour pallet contains the following colours:

Figure 2: APOLLO Colour Pallet

In order to be easily identified, all dissemination and communication material is designed using the colour pallet shown in Figure 2.

1.1.3 Templates

Based on the visual identity established by the logo and the colour pallet, templates were produced for text documents (Microsoft Word) and presentations (Microsoft PowerPoint). Templates were produced for the following types of documents:

- Deliverable documents;
- Non-Deliverable Documents, such as memos, notes or letters;
- Deliverable document reviews;
- Event reports;
- Press releases;
- Presentations.

Samples of each template are supplied in the figures below.

Figure 3: Deliverable document template

Figure 4: Non-deliverable document template

APOLLO Review Confidentiality Form

REVIEW CONFIDENTIALITY FORM

(Internal Review: Project Manager)

All external reviewers should sign a confidentiality form in order to protect the project. By signing this form you will be agreeing to the confidentiality of the information that you provide and to the fact that you will not disclose any information to anyone else. This form is to be filled in only the case of external reviewers and not those of partner institutions/members of the consortium.

DOCUMENT

WORK PACKAGE: _____

RESPONSIBLE PARTNER: _____

NAME OF REVIEWER

ORGANISATION: _____

PROFESSION: _____

SHORT ID# (up to 10 chars): _____

DECLARATION OF CONFIDENTIALITY

I hereby declare that I will treat all information, contained within the above mentioned deliverable and which has been disclosed to me through the review of this deliverable, with due confidentiality.

Signed: _____ Place and date: _____

(Internal Reviewer)

1/2

APOLLO Review Confidentiality Form

Deliverable Review

Deliverable No.:	Deliverable No.:	WP:
Project ID# (up to 10 chars):	Author(s):	

How would you rate the level of implementation in the document according to the following 6 criteria?

*NA – Not Applicable to the deliverable under review

	YES	NO	NA*
1. Does this Deliverable contain all the information I need to know and my team to continue with our work? (Where applicable)			
2. Is the data in the Deliverable complete? If not, what is missing?			
3. Is it well-structured and clear in its content? If not, explain what is lacking			
4. Is the English of good quality? (i.e. free of spelling + grammar mistakes?)			
5. Does it give a fair and inclusive picture of everybody who has contributed?			
6. Is the language used in the document gender neutral?			
Do you have any further comments or recommendations?			

Date: _____

Reviewer Signature: _____

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2/2

Figure 5: Deliverable document review template

APOLLO Event Report

(Title of Event)
(Date), (Location)
[URL of event website](#)

AIM
(Text)

AGENDA
(Brief text or image)

SUMMARY OF KEY POINTS
(Speaker), (Affiliation) - (Speaker Title)

- (Point)

PROJECTS AND INITIATIVES MENTIONED

- (Project/initiative) (URL)

KEY EVENTS

- (Event)

KEY CONTACTS

- (Contact)

PARTICIPANTS
(List or references to separate file for scanned list)

1/1

Figure 6: Event report template

Figure 7: Press release template

Figure 8: Presentation template

1.2 Website

The APOLLO website (www.apollo-h2020.eu) serves as the online marketing tool of the project. It provides key information about the project and the future commercial services. APOLLO's website provides access to the following key information in a concise and appealing manner:

- Description of project objectives, partners and funding;
- Public deliverable documents, results and latest news;
- Announcements on project activities and involvement opportunities;
- Promotional materials.

The APOLLO website was first released for comment on 28 August 2016, and formally made public in September 2016 (M05). In its first version, the website is focused on communicating the **project-related** aspects of APOLLO, whilst the second release (M12) will focus on promoting the commercial services. The structure of the project-focused website is as follows; each section heading is accompanied by a brief description of the content to be included therein:

Figure 9: APOLLO's web home page

1. **HOME:** A short synthetic description of the project, sections for tweets and news, direct links to the SERVICES page, and a link to subscribe to newsletter.

Figure 10: News and tweets section

2. **PROJECT:** A summary of the APOLLO project, with reference to the call, and the project's duration, budget and partners. The page includes:

- A list of the work packages and a short description of each, mapped against the partners, and linked to relevant other sections.
- A simple graphical timeline of the main project deployment milestones
- A list of partners with descriptions and links back to the relevant WPs;
- A list of the public deliverables along with a short description and download links of available deliverables.

Figure 11: APOLLO project section preview

3. **CONCEPT:** A discussion of the project’s background, a statement of the problems or challenges it addresses, an overview of the target markets and technologies used in the project, and a short overview of the project’s main impacts.

Figure 12: Concept section preview

4. **SERVICES:** An introduction to the service platform and its mobile application and desktop interfaces, along with a description of each of the four services, the problem each service solves, and the benefits conferred.

Figure 13: Services section preview

Figure 14: Tillage Scheduling service section preview

IRRIGATION SCHEDULING

Agricultural Irrigation uses more fresh water globally than any other activity, and therefore, improving the efficiency of water usage remains a global priority. Irrigation scheduling means using just enough water at the right time, taking into account the state of the crop, soil moisture content and the weather. Current irrigation scheduling practices involve a range of costly and time-consuming methods and equipment for determining the soil moisture and the crop water needs, including the "hand-feel" method, tensiometers, microbiological stations, electrical resistance blocks, pressure chambers and infrared thermometers. APOLLO offers a cost-effective alternative to these practices.

The APOLLO Irrigation Scheduling determines the correct frequency and duration of watering for avoiding problems caused to crops by over- and/or under- application of water.

Wet crop due to abundance of water

Dry irrigated crop

Figure 15: Irrigation Scheduling service section preview

CROP GROWTH MONITORING

The APOLLO Crop Growth Monitoring service gathers essential crop condition information (status, growth trends) during the biological cycle. Indirectly, crop growth monitoring can help in identifying different management zones at sub-parcel level for variable rate application of fertilizers and plant protection products. Current methods for monitoring crop growth include costly and time-consuming aerial or field surveys, which involve many different sensing instruments, such as hyperspectral cameras.

The APOLLO Crop Growth Monitoring service will enable farmers to keep an eye on their crops' status from emergence through to harvest, and provide early alerts in case of infestations and nutrient deficiencies.

Normal crop healthy development

Normal crop (crop infestation)

Figure 16: Crop Growth Monitoring service section preview

CROP YIELD ESTIMATION

Crop yield estimation is important for the analysis and comparison of field productivity but also it allows farmers to decide at farm level whether to sell or store the product, and for avoiding effective transfer from farm to the industry. Currently, crop yield estimation is mainly performed through time-consuming and expensive field sampling which involves the measurement of chlorophyll index and grain size.

The APOLLO Crop Yield Estimation service forecasts crop yield before harvest, allowing an assessment of the farmer's expected income, as well as enabling the adaptability of crops and/or varieties to be evaluated in combination with Crop Growth Monitoring service.

Example of a yield estimator map

Figure 17: Crop Yield Estimation service section preview

- PILOTS:** A description of each pilot (Serbia, Spain and Greece) and the partners involved, a short summary of its progress and the main results to date.

Figure 18: Pilot section preview

- NEWS & MEDIA:** A list of recent news items, links to the download sections for the newsletter (current and archive copies of web newsletter), press releases.
- GET INVOLVED:** A section dedicated to engaging with audiences, containing a contact form, newsletter subscription form, a link to the user requirements survey, and a section discussing how to become a trial user.

Figure 19: Get Involved section and web page footer

The site was produced on the basis of the WordPress platform using available templates, and modified where necessary to accommodate the required features.

1.2.1 Website statistics

APOLLO's website was put online on the 29th of August 2016, and officially launched in September (M05). Data on website traffic over this period have been monitored using Google Analytics. The major statistic indicators are the following:

- **Sessions:** Session is defined as a group of interactions taken by one user within a given time frame (30 minutes) on the website. The number of sessions is an indicator of how many times the site has been visited.
- **Users:** Visitors that have had at least one session within the selected date range (includes both new and returning visitors).
- **Page views:** the total number of times a page has been viewed. Repeated views of a single page are counted.
- **Pages/Session:** average number of pages viewed during a session. Repeated views of a single page are counted.
- **Average Session Duration:** Average time spent by visitors browsing the site.
- **Bounce Rate:** the percentage of single-page visits (i.e. visits in which the visitor enters and leaves the site from the same page, without interacting with the rest of the site).
- Percentage of **New Sessions:** estimate of the percentage of first-time visitors.

In order to remove the influence of automated web “crawlers” on the data, only sessions longer than 30 seconds have been included in the analysis. The values of the above indicators are recorded in the following table, Table 1.

Indicator	Value
Sessions	332
Users	136
Page views	577
Pages/Session	4.04
Average Session Duration	00:06:24 (h:m:s)
Bounce Rate	28.61%
New Sessions	41.87%

Table 1: Statistical indicators (launch-M06).

Information on the visitors’ behaviour and areas for improvement can be extracted from the statistical data provided by Google Analytics.

Sessions

Since launching, **the APOLLO website has received 332 visits (sessions) from 136 different users.** As can be seen in Figure 20, immediately following the official launch of the website, APOLLO received a large number of visitors. After this first peak, visits stabilised, with a few noticeable peaks occurring as a consequence of various other activities.

Figure 20: Visitor sessions for the APOLLO website (launch-M06).

As evident in Figure 21, 41.9% of total visitors to the website were new. At this point, the number of returning visitors is assumed to reflect mainly the project partners. It can be assumed that new visitors are mainly stakeholders interested in learning more about the APOLLO project, coming from the growing network of contacts established via activities such as conferences, media appearances and publications.

Figure 21: New and returning visitors (launch-M06).

Geolocation statistics

As can be seen in Figure 22, the majority of visits came from three countries: Greece (31.33% of the total sessions), Belgium (27.14% of the total sessions) and Serbia (23.19% of the total sessions), reflecting the home countries of project partners. Spanish visitors represented 4.22% of total sessions. Given the short time period since the launch of the site, a noticeable number of visits came from other European countries; Germany and France accounted for 1.20% each of the total number of sessions. In addition, there are some noteworthy visits from countries outside Europe, such as Sri Lanka (0.9%). Other international visits not shown on the graph below include the United States and India (less than 1%). Considering the recent launch of the site, these results are within the margins of expectation.

Country	Sessions	% Sessions
1. Greece	104	31.33%
2. Belgium	91	27.41%
3. Serbia	77	23.19%
4. Austria	23	6.93%
5. Spain	14	4.22%
6. Germany	4	1.20%
7. France	4	1.20%
8. Sri Lanka	3	0.90%
9. Netherlands	3	0.90%
10. Switzerland	2	0.60%

Figure 22: Visits based on country of origin launch-M06).

These statistics are expected to increase through the duration of the project as the APOLLO intensifies its dissemination and communication activities and builds solid networking channels.

1.3 Newsletter

The APOLLO project publishes a regular trimonthly newsletter to inform subscribers of upcoming events, project milestones, and relevant news stories linked to the broader fields of precision agriculture and smart farming. The main purpose of the newsletter is to announce project-related events, communicate project news, and maintain the interest and awareness of subscribers as the project progresses.

The newsletter was designed, and is distributed, using the online service MailChimp. A list of subscribers was generated by emailing a selection of contacts using the APOLLO communication database (Section 4.1), inviting subscriptions to the newsletter. This strategy was chosen to avoid sending unsolicited mail to contacts, and in the interest of retaining high-quality contacts who have opted into receiving the newsletter.

In addition, project partners were asked to distribute the newsletter amongst their contacts and publicise its availability on their own channels. The first APOLLO Newsletter was released in October 2016 and a preview of the editorial is presented in Figure 23. The complete first newsletter can be found in Annex II.

Figure 23: APOLLO's 1st Newsletter editorial

1.4 APOLLO on Social Media

Both Facebook and Twitter were designed to augment and complement the website as the central channel of stakeholders and potential customer engagement. In addition, a LinkedIn group has been created in order to stimulate debate and discussion around the APOLLO services.

1.4.1 Twitter

Twitter is a micro-publishing platform with some 330 million users, widely used for both B2B and B2C communications. Twitter can support the development of communities of interest. This is achieved through both “following” relevant accounts and being “followed”, and by the publication of short posts on the latest project developments and news, and links to relevant content. These posts are accompanied by relevant hashtags around which conversations can develop. APOLLO has established a Twitter presence under the username @APOLLO_Agri for amplifying the propagation of news, announcements and publications.

Figure 24: APOLLO's Twitter page

At the end of M06, the APOLLO Twitter account was following 101 other accounts related to the Agricultural sector (i.e. projects, private companies, agricultural professionals, EU agricultural institutions and decision makers) and was being followed by 23 other accounts.

1.4.2 Facebook

Facebook is a large and well-known social network with over 1.5 billion users, which, although designed for personal use by individuals, has become an important platform for B2C communications. APOLLO has established a Facebook page for the purpose of reaching out to groups and networks (such as Agri.EU - The Social Network of European Farmers) and for engaging in public conversations with a younger generation of technologically-aware farmers.

Figure 25: APOLLO's Facebook page

1.4.1 LinkedIn

A LinkedIn group entitled “APOLLO H2020 Project” has been formed in order to enable a platform for discussion with professionals on the network.

Figure 26: APOLLO LinkedIn Group

2 Dissemination activities

Representatives from all APOLLO project partners have promoted the project using the means and channels at their disposal.

2.1 Conferences

A strategic campaign of event and conference attendance was planned for the lifetime of the APOLLO project and is registered in “D7.1 Dissemination Communication and Marketing Plan”. The aim is to maximise the effect of direct interaction with relevant stakeholders, present the APOLLO solution as part of the programme of speakers and to distribute APOLLO marketing material to attendees. Dedicated presentations were produced by the participating partners to facilitate the promotion of APOLLO in the context of each event. A dedicated [Google form](#)¹ was created in order to collect reports from partners on the activities in which they have been involved (See Annex I).

The APOLLO project was represented at the Geospatial World Forum 2016, European Space Solutions 2016, and the NEREUS event “What can Sentinels do for regions?”. Table 1 summarises the events at which APOLLO was represented, totalling nine conferences and workshops.

Event	Description	APOLLO's involvement
<p>Copernicus Eastern Europe Conference: “Copernicus – big data benefitting environment and society”</p> <p>Bucharest, 1-2 October 2015</p> <p>Participation: EVF</p> <p>Session: Regional Copernicus activities and their potential for cooperation</p> <p>Materials: PPT presentation</p> <p>No. of attendees: ~70</p>	<p>The conference is a reference event for the Earth Observation community in Eastern Europe. The 2015 conference demonstrated the progress made by the European Union flagship programme towards providing reliable data benefitting environment and security.</p> <p>More about the event can be found here.</p>	<p>The APOLLO project was presented in order to initiate contacts and to build a network across Europe with the members of the EO community.</p> <p>Presentation title: “An advisory platform for small-scale farmers based on Copernicus data: the APOLLO project”, Dimitrios Papadakis (EVF).</p>
<p>Copernicus Value Chain Workshop</p> <p>Brussels, 26-27 April 2016</p> <p>Participation: EVF</p> <p>Session: Supporting end-users and boosting demand for</p>	<p>The workshop aimed at identifying specific needs and expectations from the widest possible range of stakeholders and communities to foster the full development of the Copernicus Value Chain. It gathered a mix of representatives from the Copernicus ecosystem, actors from the information</p>	<p>Dimitrios Papadakis (EVF) attended this event in order to collect observations relevant to the project and make connections with the stakeholders present.</p>

¹ A preview of the Google form can be found in Annex I.

<p>EO enabled services</p> <p>Materials: none</p> <p>No. of attendees: ~100</p>	<p>technology industry and big data domain, as well as existing and potential end-users of Copernicus data and information from a variety of industrial sectors. Two themes were addressed: data dissemination platforms for Copernicus and market uptake of Copernicus, including support to companies in the EO downstream sector.</p> <p>More about the event can be found here.</p>	
<p>Geospatial World Forum – CAPIGI</p> <p>Rotterdam, 24-26 May 2016</p> <p>Participation: EVF</p> <p>Session: CAPIGI and GeoAGRI</p> <p>Materials: PPT presentation</p> <p>No. of attendees: ~40 (CAPIGI); ~400 (GWF)</p>	<p>CAPIGI is the network for geo-information experts active in agriculture. The Community on Agricultural Policy Implementation and Geo-Information (CAPIGI) brings together governments, industry and research to discuss the impact of geo-information in implementing agricultural policy. CAPIGI presents a state-of-the-art overview on innovations and research in geo-information sciences. These emerging technologies get illustrated with practice experiences in agricultural policy implementation.</p> <p>More information as well as images from the event can be found here.</p>	<p>In the framework of establishing a solid network within the EO and the Agricultural community, Mr Papadakis presented the services and solutions as well as the vision for creating an operational commercial platform.</p> <p>Presentation title: “An advisory platform for small farmers”, Dimitrios Papadakis, Evenflow.</p>
<p>European Space Solutions</p> <p>Hague, 30 May-03 June 2016</p> <p>Participation: EVF</p> <p>Session: Agriculture and Food</p> <p>Materials: none</p> <p>No. of attendees: ~350</p>	<p>Under the auspices of the 2016 Dutch Presidency of the Council of the EU, the fourth successful edition of European Space Solutions took place in The Hague from 30 May 3 June 2016 at the World Forum Convention Centre. This major 5-day conference brought together business and the public sector with users and developers of space-based solutions.</p> <p>More information as well as images from the event can be</p>	<p>Dimitrios Papadakis (EVF) attended this event in order to collect observations relevant to the project and make connections with the stakeholders present.</p>

	found here .	
<p>What can Sentinels do for regions? (Sentinels4Regions)</p> <p>Brussels, 28 June 2016</p> <p>Participation: EVF</p> <p>Session: all</p> <p>Materials: none</p> <p>No. of attendees: ~60</p>	<p>The joint NEREUS-ESA initiative on "Improving Copernicus among Local and Regional Authorities" held its final festive event at the European Parliament, under the auspices of Patrizia Toia, Member of European Parliament and Vice-Chair of the ITRE Committee.</p> <p>More information for the event can be found here.</p>	<p>Dimitrios Papadakis (EVF) attended this event in order to collect observations relevant to the project and make connections with the stakeholders present.</p>
<p>Copernicus Agri Forestry User Requirements Workshop</p> <p>Brussels, 30 June 2016</p> <p>Participation: EVF</p> <p>Session: Agriculture and Food Security</p> <p>Materials: none</p> <p>No. of attendees: ~60</p>	<p>This workshop aimed at gathering, examining and consolidating user requirements, and confronting these with major gaps to be potentially addressed by the Next Generation of the Copernicus Space Component (CSC).</p> <p>The workshop had two sessions, one dedicated to the Agriculture and Food Security domain, and another with focus on Forestry applications.</p> <p>More information as well as images from the event can be found here.</p>	<p>The audience was composed of users, service providers, representatives from the scientific community, and Space agencies. Dimitrios Papadakis (EVF) attended this event in order to collect observations relevant to the project and make connections with the stakeholders present.</p>
<p>GeoMLA (Geostatistics and Machine Learning) – Applications in Climate and Environmental Sciences</p> <p>Belgrade, 23 June 2016</p> <p>Participation: UBFCE</p> <p>Session: II</p> <p>Materials: PPT presentation</p> <p>No. of attendees: ~50</p>	<p>The GeoMLA conference aims at reviewing the recent progress in the application of Machine learning and geostatistics in Climate and Environmental sciences. The conference sessions covered topics including modelling of climate science data, spatio-temporal predictions in 2D, 3D, 2D+T and 3D+T, novel approaches to automated mapping and geoinformatics for Environmental sciences, combining geostatistics and machine learning, change detection and temporal analysis of meteorological and climatic variables.</p>	<p>Dr Dragutin Protic gave a presentation explaining how biophysical parameters derived from Sentinel-2 data enable crop condition monitoring.</p>

<p>Science Communication Event – Manchester</p> <p>Manchester, 24 July 2016</p> <p>Participation: EVF</p> <p>Session: all</p> <p>Materials: PPT presentation</p> <p>No. of attendees: ~250</p>	<p>The focus of this event was on highlighting the benefits of science communication and better understanding the interests of different communication multipliers such as for example the European Commission, journalists, and big organisations promoting science to the general public.</p> <p>During the event, invited experts explained their views on science communication and particularly why they believe communication is beneficial for researchers, the do's and don'ts in communication and how to work together.</p> <p>More information as well as images from the event can be found here.</p>	<p>The event was designed to allow discussion between H2020 projects on their science communication strategies. On behalf of APOLLO, Dimitrios Papadakis (EVF) attended this event in order to collect observations relevant to the project and make connections with relevant stakeholders present. Initially it was intended that presentation should be given but this was cancelled in the lead-up to the event.</p>
<p>APOLLO Interactive Stakeholder Workshop</p> <p>Ruma, 29 July 2016</p> <p>Participation: UPOR, UBFCE</p> <p>Session: All</p> <p>Materials: PPT</p> <p>No. of attendees: ~60</p>	<p>Ugljesa Trkulja from the Association of farmers of the Municipality of Ruma and Dragutin Protic and Milan Kilibarda, both from the Faculty of Civil Engineering of the University of Belgrade, led an interactive workshop with approximately sixty farmers, consultants and representatives of agricultural cooperatives from the Municipality of Ruma and its surrounding area. The aim was to present the ideas of the APOLLO project to farmers, consultants and cooperatives of the Municipality of Ruma, to raise their awareness regarding the use of satellite data in agriculture and to prompt their interest in actively participating in the creation of APOLLO services.</p>	<p>APOLLO-organised stakeholder consultant and awareness-raising event.</p>
<p>INSPIRE Conference 2016- “INSPIRing a sustainable environment”</p> <p>Barcelona, 26-30</p>	<p>The INSPIRE Conference 2016 aimed to demonstrate how the implementation of INSPIRE contributes to the European Interoperability Framework and the EU's digital economy in</p>	<p>Dimitrios Papadakis (EVF) attended this event in order to collect observations relevant to the project and make connections with the</p>

September 2016 Participation: EVF Session: INSPIRE + COPERNICUS Materials: n/a No. of attendees: ~700	general. More information as well as images from the event can be found here .	stakeholders present.
European Space Expo Brussels, 25 October 2016 Participation: EVF Materials: PPT presentation No. of attendees: ~50	The Expo presents key information on the European space programmes - from satellite navigation (Galileo and EGNOS) to Earth observation (Copernicus) – to the general public in an engaging and entertaining way.	The APOLLO services and objectives were presented to the general public by Dimitrios Papadakis (EVF). APOLLO's at the event aimed to raise the awareness of the general audience regarding the benefits of space technologies in daily life.

Table 2: Conferences and workshops at which APOLLO was represented (M0-M06)

2.2 Publications

Publishing articles in qualified publications guarantees the effective dissemination of specific project results, targeting groups of experts in the sectors addressed by APOLLO. For this reason, a set of conferences and scientific journals were identified. In the scientific domain publishing results in peer-reviewed journals, and in peer-reviewed conferences is the dominant mechanism for knowledge transfer. During the first six months of the project, one conference paper was published and presented by its lead author Dr. Dragutin Protic at the GeoMLA conference in Belgrade in May 2016:

- D. Protić, S. Milutinović, O. Antonijević, A. Sekulić, M. Kilibarda, “*Sensitivity of vegetation indices derived from Sentinel-2 data to change in biophysical characteristics*”, in proceedings of Geostatistical and Machine Learning Applications and Environmental Sciences (GeoMLA), Belgrade, Serbia, 21-24 June 2016.

The number of publications and conference papers is expected to increase as the project's technological development advances.

2.3 Media

Since the start of the project on the 1st of March 2016, representatives of the consortium have promoted the project in the media, through regional TV interviews and articles in national news.

2.3.1 Serbia

- Article in Serbian regional journal, published on the 18th June 2016:

[“Прецизна пољопривреда- Аполо пројекат”](#)

(EN: Precision Agriculture – APOLLO project)

This article presents the aims, objectives and consortium of the APOLLO project. It also gives access to a brief video report of a meeting organised by the project with local farmers' associations.

- Article and video on Serbian regional channel: STV SREMSKA TELEVIZIJA, 29 June 2016
 - [“Satelitsko praćenje poljoprivrednih useva u Rumi”](#)

(EN: “Satellites monitoring agricultural crops in Ruma”)

This article presents the aim, the objectives and the consortium of the APOLLO project.

- [TV coverage and interview](#)

Presentation of the APOLLO project and services to representatives of the agricultural community in Serbia and interview with Dr. Dragutin Protic.

2.3.2 Greece

- Article on Agrenda.gr, published on the 23rd September 2016:

[“APOLLO: Η ΕΦΑΡΜΟΓΗ ΠΟΥ ΕΠΙΤΡΕΠΕΙ ΣΤΟΥΣ ΑΓΡΟΤΕΣ ΝΑ... ΚΑΛΙΕΡΓΟΥΝ ΑΠΟ ΜΑΚΡΙΑ”](#)

(EN: APOLLO: an application that enables farmers to cultivate remotely)

This article presents the aim, the objectives and the services of the APOLLO project.

3 Conclusions

This Dissemination Report has provided an overview of the dissemination, communication and marketing activities implemented in the scope of the APOLLO project, in accordance with the provisions of the Dissemination Plan “D7.1: Dissemination, communication and marketing plan” issued during the first months of the project (M03).

The effectiveness of these activities has been ensured by defining appropriate target groups, allowing the most relevant audiences to be reached with the most appropriate dissemination and communication tools and activities. The main aim is to keep the interested parties engaged with the project and its results, with the ultimate intention of converting them into customers.

Participation in various events such as workshops, conferences and networking events is an important activity for gathering opinions and creating partnerships. As a result of the various events at which APOLLO has been represented, a solid basis for future cooperation has begun to form. Partners have successfully embarked on building networks of contacts who are interested in the APOLLO services. Involvement in the outreach activities mentioned above has allowed the enrichment of the market knowledge of the APOLLO team and has provided meaningful insights into the key competitors and their practices.

Along with the target groups identified, a wider audience has been reached through the participation of APOLLO representatives in international conferences, as well as the publication of papers in specialised publications.

4 References

- European Commission, 2012. The use of the EU emblem in the context of EU programmes: Guidelines for beneficiaries and other third parties, October 2012.

5 Annexes

Annex I: APOLLO Dissemination Report

APOLLO Dissemination Report

May-October 2016

This form is for reporting APOLLO dissemination activities during the above time period. Please note that events should be reported using the Event Report template available in Dropbox\APOLLO\Templates.

* Απαιτείται

Διεύθυνση ηλεκτρονικού ταχυδρομείου *

Η διεύθυνσή σας ηλεκτρονικού ταχυ...

Partner *

Επιλογή ▾

Activity type *

Επιλογή ▾

Date(s) and place of activity (if applicable)

Η απάντησή σας

Description of activity

Η απάντησή σας

Audience (size/demographics)

Η απάντησή σας

Key stakeholders

Η απάντησή σας

Feedback / impact

Η απάντησή σας

Promotional material used

Η απάντησή σας

Material produced (e.g. photos, videos, presentations etc.)

Η απάντησή σας

ΥΠΟΒΟΛΗ

Σελίδα 1 από 1

Μην υποβάλλετε ποτέ κωδικούς πρόσβασης μέσω των Φορμών Google.

Annex II: APOLLO's 1st Newsletter

[View this email in your browser.](#)

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APOLLO NEWSLETTER | October 2016

A P O L L O

Agricultural advisory services for European farmers

Welcome to the first newsletter of the APOLLO project, an EU-funded initiative aiming to build **affordable, accessible and easy-to-use agricultural advisory services** for European farmers - especially smallholders.

The field of precision agriculture is making great strides thanks to the increasing availability (and ever-decreasing price) of a wide variety of technologies, such as drones, sensors and cloud data processing, as well as vast quantities of free and open

This project is co-funded
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data provided by the Copernicus programme.

APOLLO harnesses the power of satellite imagery and state-of-the-art crop models to make the benefits of precision agriculture accessible to farmers who might not otherwise be able to take advantage of them. Our consortium is working hard to creating an affordable, tailored product to meet the needs of the many small farmers in Europe who have yet to benefit from the latest technological developments in precision agriculture, which are often expensive, and only make economic sense for farmers with large holdings.

We are looking forward to an exciting project with real commercial potential, and we welcome your comments and feedback as we move forward.

- *The APOLLO Communications Team*

APOLLO News

A successful project launch

The APOLLO project was successfully launched at its inaugural meeting, held in Thessaloniki on the 12th and 13th of May 2016. [Read the press release!](#)

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Farmers in the driver's seat
APOLLO reaches out to farmers in the three pilot countries of Serbia, Greece and Spain to gather views on what the future services should do.

[Read more about APOLLO's user consultation](#)

Validating the demand of APOLLO services
The APOLLO project was represented at two major conferences this summer where the increasing potential of new applications in the precision agriculture field was repeatedly emphasised.

[Read more](#)

Sentinel-2 data enables crop monitoring
Dr Dragutin Protic explains how biophysical parameters derived from Sentinel-2 data enable crop condition monitoring, at the Geostatistics and Machine Learning conference.

[Watch the video](#)

Meet the APOLLO team

An interview with Machi Simeonidou (DRAXIS), APOLLO Project Coordinator
APOLLO's coordinator Machi Simeonidou, project manager at DRAXIS Environmental Technologies, gives her perspective on the implementation of the APOLLO project's vision.

[Read the interview with Machi Simeonidou.](#)

Discover APOLLO!

Bringing the benefits of precision agriculture to smallholder farmers

APOLLO is an EU project aiming to develop agricultural advisory services aimed primarily (but not exclusively) at smallholder farmers in Europe.

[Visit the APOLLO project's new web site!](#)

The APOLLO Services

Tillage Scheduling

When to till for best results, avoiding soil degradation and saving energy.

Irrigation Scheduling

When and how much to water your crops, reduce waste and avoid over-irrigating.

Crop Growth Monitoring

Keep an eye on the state and health of crops from emergence to harvest.

Crop Yield Estimation

Analyse field productivity and improve sell/store decision making.

This project is co-funded by the European Union

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Events on the horizon

[NEREUS Regional Workshop: When Space Meets Agriculture](#)

14-15 November 2016, Matera, Italy

Promoting a better understanding of the significance and potential of European space systems in Agriculture.

[European Intelligent Agriculture Congress](#)

16-17 February 2017, Brussels, Belgium

The congress will feature, displays and presentations of currently available and near future agri-tech innovation.

News from the field

[The Agrinnovation magazine Issue No 3 is out!](#)

Read how research and practice come together in action in EIP-Agri's annual journal.

[Precision agriculture could be the solution to feeding 10 billion people](#)

Read why precision agriculture innovations help to meet the world's food demand and potentially benefit all levels of the farming industry.

[Review: Costs and benefits of precision technologies 'poorly understood'](#)

A survey on the barriers to the adoption and development of precision farming technologies within the cereals and oilseeds sector, published in FarmingUK.

[How ICT tools are improving the efficiency of agricultural development](#)

A survey from the Guardian on the added value of new tools used in agriculture.

[Adaptation strategies to deal with water scarcity](#)

Read how to improve water management at farm level in EIP-Agri's factsheet.

[Launch of new satellites have potential to help farmers take precision agriculture to](#)

[next level](#)

An article on how the Copernicus programme has the potential to enable farmers take precision agriculture to a new level, published in FarmingUK.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 687412

Disclaimer

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